

Sensitivity of public debt to macroeconomic shocks: An application to the Egyptian economy

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Abstract: This paper aims at assessing the vulnerability of public debt to various shocks in macroeconomic variables in Egypt. This is particularly relevant for the Egyptian economy since it has currently witnessed high levels of public debt and has adopted a structural reform program that encompasses fiscal and monetary reforms to ensure macroeconomic stability. Hence, it is crucial to provide insights to policy makers on the most influential variables that affect the public debt to boost the reform efforts and guarantee fiscal sustainability. Accordingly, this work utilizes a structural vector auto regressive model (SVAR) for the Egyptian economy during the period (2005-2015) to investigate the relationship between gross public debt and a set of macroeconomic, monetary and fiscal variables. The results indicate a positive relationship between government debt and major economic variables - except inflation and government revenues. A positive shock in economic growth, government expenditures, real effective exchange rates or interest rates are all expected to cause a higher level of public debt. This result is consistent with the upward trend of rising public debt through the time interval of the study. Meanwhile, an increase in the inflation rate erodes the real value of public debt, and hence has a negative impact on the debt-to-GDP ratio. Finally, an increase in government revenues leads to a reduction in the debt-to-GDP ratio but after a transitory period of 3 quarters. This negative relationship does not occur instantly, as it takes time to reverse the upward trend in public debt and overcome the inclination to borrow more even if revenues are increasing. Consequently, sufficient measures need to be taken to ensure a sustainable increase in government revenues, while cutting and prioritizing government expenditures to decrease the overall level of public debt.

JEL Classifications: H63, E60, E63, C50

Keywords: Public debt, economic growth, inflation, government budget, interest rates, exchange rates, SVAR, Egypt

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1. Introduction

One of the most controversial economic issues that have been receiving greater interest in both emerging and advanced economies is the one related to government or public debt. Public debt is defined as the total financial obligations in local and foreign currencies (domestic and external debt) incurred by the governmental bodies of a nation. The importance of studying and analyzing public debt arises from two main facts: First, government's borrowing decisions have a great direct impact upon almost all economic indicators, in addition to a wide variety of social and political indicators. These borrowing decisions have influential effect on the creditworthiness and the reliability of the economy both internally and externally, and to a great extent on the quality of living inside the country. Second, public debt does not only affect the stance of economic indicators, but it is also very sensitive to changes in a variety of macroeconomic, monetary and fiscal

economic indicators. Changes in those indicators are expected to have a vital impact upon fiscal decisions; particularly those related to borrowing from inside or outside the country.

In this regard, the aim of this study is to analyze the sensitivity of gross public debt to a set of macroeconomic, monetary and fiscal indicators. The analysis is applied on the Egyptian Economy during the period (2005-2015). Throughout its modern history, Egypt has always witnessed relatively high levels of public debt. However, it has recently reached unprecedented levels due to the increase in government expenditures and deterioration of key sources of national income after the 2011 uprising. The recent devaluation of the Egyptian pound in November 2016 is also one of the major factors that affected the cost of external borrowing and, therefore, the total level of gross public debt. Examining how the level of debt is expected to respond to changes in the economic environment gives a lot of crucial insights for the both the government and the economic community regarding the sustainability of public debt.

Hence, the main research question that the paper seeks to answer is to what extent the changes in economic variables affect gross public debt in Egypt. More specifically, the paper is interested in studying the impact of changes in government revenues, government expenditures, inflation rate, interest rates and exchange rates upon the total value of government debt. Although the relationship between debt and major economic variables has been examined in the literature before; the analysis of this paper differs for two reasons. First, the majority of the existing literature has been interested in examining how changes in public debt affect the behavior of different economic variables, but not the opposite as intended by this paper. Second, the paper applies on the Egyptian economy, which was not analyzed in the same context before. Furthermore, the relative importance of the paper is strengthened by its time span that covers a major change in the Egyptian Economy - through applying the Structural Reform Program - and which have great impact upon the borrowing decisions of the government. Both points reflect the main contribution of the paper.

Towards this objective, the paper utilizes a SVAR approach to model the impact of various macroeconomic variables on public debt. This is crucial to assess public debt sustainability and analyze the most influential shocks in affecting government debt. Using quarterly data for the period (2005-2015) for Egypt, the model seeks to study the sensitivity of gross government debt to changes in economic growth, inflation, government budget, interest rates and exchange rates.

Accordingly, the paper is divided into five sections in addition to the introduction and the conclusion. Section two examines the existing literature review regarding the relationship between public debt and various macroeconomic, fiscal and monetary indicators. Section three analyzes the background of government debt in Egypt; through analyzing its trend and composition over the period (2000-2017). In Section four, we present the methodological framework. Specifically, the section starts first by introducing the data and variables used in the analysis, and then the details of the econometric model. The results of the model and their implications are discussed in section five.

2. Literature review

A vast array of studies have examined the relationship between public debt and several macroeconomic variables; the majority of those studies were interested in examining how

do different levels of government debt are expected to affect the behavior of economic variables. Only very few studies have attempted to analyze the reverse causality between gross government debt and macroeconomic variables. In this regard, one of the main contributions of this paper is investigating how changes in the different fiscal, monetary and macro variables are expected to affect public debt. Particularly, we are interested in analyzing the relation between gross government debt and a set of variables, namely: economic growth, inflation, government revenues, government expenditures, interest rates, and exchange rates.

Concerning the relation between government debt and economic growth, most studies have concluded that in the long-run public debt has a negative impact on economic growth through a standard crowding out effect. This conclusion was supported by the results of many empirical studies that have proven the above relationship in advanced and emerging economies. The correlation is particularly strong when public debt reaches 100 percent of GDP (see for example, Diamond, 1965; Saint-Paul, 1992; Schclarek, 2004; Adam & Bevan, 2005; Aizenman, Kletzer, & Pinto, 2007). However, much less interest was given to the reverse relationship; how changes in economic growth shall affect public debt. The intended causality in this case is the one going from growth to debt and not vice-versa; only few studies have examined this reversed causality.

Among those few, Cherif & Hassanov (2012) examined how macroeconomic shocks affect U.S. public debt dynamics using a VAR analysis. They found that a positive growth shock lowers debt and hence a negative response of public debt ratio to changes in GDP. Higher output growth indicates a stronger economy with less reliance on government borrowing. Checherita-Westphal & Rother (2011) also confirmed this negative reverse causation; low or negative growth rates of per capita GDP are likely to induce higher debt burdens. Given the narrowed available studies on this reversed causality, more evidence is still needed before we could reach a concrete result regarding the impact of economic growth on gross debt figures. Our paper is one step towards this objective.

Public debt is also expected to respond to changes in monetary variables like inflation, interest, and exchange rates. In this regard, the existing literature is greatly limited to studying the impact of public debt on monetary variables and not the opposite. In literature, there is a main strand arguing that higher inflation can lead to a reduction in public debt as higher prices erode the real value of public debt. Akitoby et al. (2014) conducted simulations to investigate the impact of inflation on public debt in G7 countries. The results showed that an increase in the inflation rate to reach 6% for five consecutive years would lead to a reduction in the average net debt by about 11 percentage points by the end of the period under the full fisher effect, and this percentage increases to 14% under partial fisher effect.

These findings are also consistent with empirical findings in developing countries. Nguyen (2015) investigated the impact of inflation on public debt in 60 developing countries in Asia, Africa and Latin America over the period 1990-2014. The results showed that inflation has a significant negative effect on debt, although in the opposite direction debt was found to have a significant positive impact on inflation. Reinhart et al. (2015) also showed that inflation is an option that is used to significantly reduce debt in highly indebted countries when the major portion of public debt comes from domestic debt.

Regarding the relationship between public debt and interest rates; the hypothesis is that higher interest rates will raise interest costs on the National Debt; higher short- and long-

term Treasury rates mean that the government's domestic borrowing costs will also rise. Hence; the expected response of public debt to interest rate hikes is a positive response through augmenting the value of domestic debt. Indeed, a number of studies have confirmed this relationship; for example, Wen (2016) have been interested in quantitatively measuring the budgetary impact of a rise in domestic interest rates on the cost of servicing the government debt, through analyzing different scenarios of rate hikes in Ontario, Canada. With the same objective also, Faria-e-Castro (2018) attempted to investigate the projected impact of rising interest payments on the federal deficit and debt. The study concluded that given that interest payments are likely to double in the next 10 years (due to higher interest rates and higher federal debt), this would create upward pressure on federal deficits. The deficits are likely to be higher and may range from 7 to 10 percent of GDP, depending on the projected inputs.

Real exchange rate movements should be thoroughly taken into consideration while studying the sensitivity of public debt to economic shocks; particularly through its effect on the external component of the debt. According to economic theory, a higher exchange rate (number of domestic currencies per one foreign currency) indicates a depreciation in the value of the domestic currency. A lower value of the domestic currency in turns indicates a higher cost of external borrowing. The level of foreign debt is, therefore, supposed to increase to indicate a higher level of debt service. Thus, the relationship between public debt and exchange rates is expected to be positive.

Melecky & Melecky (2011) supported this positive relationship; they found that the fiscal stance in the Czech Republic is most vulnerable to an unexpected local currency depreciation which initially generates more revenues through a positive income effect, but later on the negative balance sheet effect takes over and produces a significant negative response. Carrera & Vergara (2012) also found that a devaluation of the local currency can significantly change the path of a sustainable fiscal policy through changes in the value of the foreign-currency-denominated debt; therefore, confirming the positive response of public debt to lower currency values (higher exchange rates).

However, some other studies (for example, Sávai & Kiss, 2017) did not find any significant relationship between changes in Real Effective Exchange rates and public debt. Public debt arises to finance the budget deficit due to the excess of government spending over government revenues. Thus, public debt increases as government expenditures increase when domestic revenues are not sufficient to cover this spending.

Similarly, public debt tends to decrease with increases in the mobilized public revenues which lead to a reduction in budget deficit. Budina & Fiess (2005) investigated the determinants of public debt in 15 countries, and found evidence that public debt decreases with increases in fiscal surplus. Similarly, Mah, Mukkudem-Petersen, Miruka & Petersen (2013) found a significant positive relationship between government expenditures and public debt in Greece during the period from 1976 to 2011.

Thus, countries should aim at adopting sound fiscal policies to reduce public debt. Similarly, Uguru (2016) found that there is a significant positive relationship between government expenditures and public debt in Nigeria during the period from 1980-2013. Thus, he concluded that the Nigerian government should promote efforts towards cutting current expenditures to reduce public debt and achieve long-term fiscal sustainability.

3. Trend and composition of public debt in Egypt: An analytical review

3.1. Public debt in Egypt: Background

Public debt has been representing a serious problem in Egypt during the past few years; especially during the post- revolutionary period since 2011. During its history, Egypt had been suffering from rising levels of debt that reached extraordinary records during the recent years; reaching 103% of GDP in 2017. High borrowing rates are in many cases attributed to the increased levels of government spending and the decline in the sources of revenues of national income. Over the period (1985-2016), the growth rate of government debt was higher than the overall growth rate of the Egyptian economy (Mossallem, 2017). After 2000, the increased public spending in inefficient sectors, the escalation in the costs of imported materials, together with the high subsidies, and the wages of employees led to rapid growth of the public debt (El-Mahdy & Torayeh, 2009). From 2000 to 2009, Egypt's level of debt increased by around 15 percent, despite the fact that the country paid a total of 24.6 billion USD in debt repayments over the same period. The main increase came from the country's agreements with the International Financial Institutions.

Government Debt to GDP in Egypt averaged approximately 89 percent from 2002 until 2010, peaking at approximately 103 percent in 2017 and reaching its lowest at 73.3 percent in 2009 (Figure 1). Debt servicing as a percentage of total expenditure averaged 27 percent with interest payments alone constituting the third highest expenditure item after wages and subsidies (El-Ghouty, 2018). Since 2010, Egypt has been facing a growing budget deficit, until it reached 9.5 percent of GDP in 2017. Deficits were rising as revenues were declining due to the economic recession that followed the revolution, in addition to the reluctance to progressively raise income taxes or undergo expenditure reform due to its high political cost - almost 80 % of the state budget allocated to wages, subsidies and debt services (Mossallem, 2017). Over the last five years, and within the implementation of the New Economic Reform Program with the IMF, total government debt has been increasing at unprecedented rates reaching 3.1 trillion EGP in 2017.

FIGURE 1. EVOLUTION AND COMPOSITION OF GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

The profile of government debt in Egypt is characterized by a high share of domestic debt; reaching a peak of 85% of gross government debt in 2016. Before 1990, external debt, rather than domestic debt, was the major concern of Egyptian policy makers. However, since the launch of ERSAP, domestic debt has become the main source of debt. Domestic debt rose sharply under ERSAP, surpassing external debt both in terms of stock ratios to GDP as well as flows of debt-service expenditure. The share of domestic debt over total debt climbed from 40 percent in the early 1990s to about 65 percent in 2000/2001.

The mounting increase in domestic debt since the start of the 90s can be attributed to two factors. First, in response to the massive capital flows as a result of the liberalization of capital flows under the ERSAP, the government responded with a sterilization program. The Central Bank acquired foreign currency in return for the sale of domestic securities, particularly Treasury Bills. Therefore, in addition to exchange rate problems, capital inflows caused a domestic debt problem. The second factor contributing to the rise in domestic debt was the decline in state revenues and the gradual rise in public deficits. State revenue steadily declined from around 30 percent of Egypt's GDP in the late 1980s to 20 percent of GDP by the year 2000, while expenditure stagnated at around 30-32 percent of GDP. Since then, domestic debt has been increasing at a steady state until 2016 representing the major source of financing government's expenditures. In 2017, and as a response to the currency devaluation, the percentage of external debt increased in lie with the IMF reforming program, and the percentage of domestic debt started to decline accordingly (Mossallem, 2017).

FIGURE 2. EVOLUTION AND COMPOSITION OF DOMESTIC GOVERNMENT DEBT (2005-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

Note: Left chart shows domestic government debt, mln. EGP. Right chart shows percentage composition of domestic government debt.

Domestic debt is mainly concentrated in Egyptian government loans financed via individuals, banks and non-banking institutions. Egypt's domestic debt has kept increasing in the last 5 years, reaching unprecedented levels in June 2017, where it reached about EGP 3.2 trillion compared to EGP 888.7 billion in June 2010. This increase is mainly attributed to the fact that government expenditures have been increasing at a faster pace than its revenues, leading to a rising budget deficit and a steady increase of indebtedness accordingly. On the expenditures side, different items like wages, interest payments,

subsidies and public investments have significantly increased after the breakout of the 2011 Revolution, while state revenues, especially tax proceeds, were negatively affected by the witnessed political and economic instability (El-Ghouty, 2018).

The composition of net domestic debt of government, which represents more than 80% of total domestic debt (Figure 2) comes from five sources: (A) Balances of Bonds and Bill, (B) Borrowing from other entities, (C) Credit Facilities from the Social Insurance Funds, (D) The Masri Dollar certificate, and (E) Net Government Balances with the Banking System. Around 80% of domestic debt is being financed through the government issuance of T-Bills and Bonds (3 trillion in 2017).

FIGURE 3. EVOLUTION AND COMPOSITION OF EXTERNAL GOVERNMENT DEBT (2005-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

Note: Left chart shows external government debt, min. USD. Right chart shows percentage composition of external government debt.

External debt is defined as government loans attained in foreign currency from international creditors. In Egypt, it had an upward trend during the period from June 2010 to June 2015, representing 15% of GDP at the end of this period. This increase is mainly attributed to the decrease in key sources of foreign currency after 2011, including tourism revenues, exports and FDIs. Egypt's external debt of all maturities increased as a result of the rise in net disbursements of loans and facilities, and the depreciation of most currencies of borrowing versus the US dollar. In this regards, Egypt's external debt has jumped by almost 60 percent since 2010, rising from 33.7 billion USD in 2010 to 79 billion USD in March 2017. By the end of 2017, Egypt has acquired a 12 billion USD from the IMF causing an additional increase in external borrowing to reach a record high percentage of 31% of gross Government debt.

Egypt's external debt mainly consists of loans from foreign governments and regional & international monetary agencies like the World Bank and the IMF. It also includes bonds offered in international markets and deposits held by the Central Bank of Egypt. The sources of external financing of government expenditures are international and regional organizations, long term deposits, Egyptian bonds and notes, rescheduled bilateral debt, suppliers' and buyers' credit, other bilateral debt, and non-guaranteed private sector debt.

3.2. Gross government debt and macroeconomic variables in Egypt

In this section, the paper investigates the relationship between total government debt and the different macroeconomic variables reflecting the scope of the study. This descriptive analysis is useful as a prior investigation of the response of debt to the various macroeconomic shocks; before it is formally inspected using more advanced quantitative methods in the next section. Therefore, using annual Egyptian data for the period (2000-2017), the relationship between government debt and each of economic growth, inflation, government revenues and expenditures, interest rates and real effective exchange rate will be depicted and analyzed. Figure (4) shows the relationship between economic growth (measured by Real Gross Domestic Product RGDP) and each of gross to debt ratio and the percent change of gross debt which we use as a proxy for gross debt.

FIGURE 4. ECONOMIC GROWTH AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

Both charts show a positive relationship between RGDP and gross government debt; whether as a percentage of GDP or as a growth rate; though with different slopes. The relationship is stronger when using growth rate of gross debt. The increase in economic capacity, as reflected by a higher level of output, is expected to lead to higher debt levels. Given the low capacity of the Egyptian economy to generate revenues from domestic sources in lieu with the recent economic crises that the economy faced following the 2011 uprising; there is higher chance of increasing reliance on borrowing as a main source of finance. Therefore, this positive relationship suggests that as the level of income increase (measured by RGDP) inside the economy, the government will lean towards financing the economic activities through increasing its gross borrowing.

The decisions concerning government debt is highly affected by the change in the government budget; the changes in both the expenditures and revenues sides are expected to leave an impact upon government debt. An increase in government expenditures causing a higher budget deficit will require an increase in government debt to finance the higher government spending. Therefore, the relationship between government expenditures and gross government debt is positive; whether debt is measured by the Debt to GDP ratio, or by the growth rate of gross debt. Using the later shows a stronger

relationship though indicating that not only the value of Debt increase, but that the rate of increase is even higher. Figure (5) shows this relationship.

FIGURE 5. GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURES AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

According to economic theory and existing literature review, an increase in government revenues is expected to cause a downward change in government debt in the sense that the government is able to finance its expenditure with the higher level of revenues. Accordingly the relationship would be expected to be negative.

FIGURE 6. GOVERNMENT REVENUES AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

However, as Figure (6) shows, the relationship between government revenues and gross government debt is positive; indicating that an increase in government revenues would induce the government to borrow more not less. This relationship could be interpreted by referring to the Egyptian context. Generally speaking, since the mid-1980s, Egypt’s fiscal policy has not been a purely domestic issue. In fact, the external relationship between Egypt and the international community had and still have a growing influence on the policies adopted; particularly those related to borrowing decisions. Several examples could

be drawn; one of them is dated to the 80s, when debt service had reached almost 100 percent of gross new borrowings. Even though the Egyptian economy experienced an influx of revenues, the government was still inclined to borrow and to demand more aid from abroad (Mossallem, 2017). This unexpected behavior of the Egyptian economy is in fact a big support to the positive relationship reached between government revenues and debt; showing that in multiple instances the government could still borrow more even though its revenues are increasing.

FIGURE 7. INFLATION AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

FIGURE 8. INTEREST RATES AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

In addition to economic growth rate and government budget, government debt is also affected by a set of monetary variables like inflation, interest, and exchange rates. All of those variables are expected to have a direct impact upon government borrowing decisions. As Figure (7) shows, the relationship between inflation and government debt is positive; indicating that a higher price level induces the government to borrow more. This

is quite expected, an increase in inflation rate means more expensive expenditures for the government and hence more financing requirements.

Interest rates are also one of the main monetary variables that is expected to affect gross government debt (Figure 8). Using treasury bills rate as a proxy for interest rates, the relationship with both debt to GDP ratio the growth rate of gross debt is positive. An increase in interest rate will increase government borrowing due to the higher costs of financing public debts.

FIGURE 9. REAL EFFECTIVE EXCHANGE RATES AND GROSS GOVERNMENT DEBT IN EGYPT (2000-2017)

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

A major factor contributing to the analysis of government debt is exchange rates. It has a direct impact upon the cost of external borrowing, and is often considered as an essential influential aspect guiding the decision of external borrowing. In this regard, real effective exchange rate (REER) is most commonly used as a representative indicator of exchange rates through taking into account the effect of price changes. In the end of 2016, Egypt has witnessed a huge change in its exchange rate system through the CBE decision of floating the Egyptian pound in November to signal a new era of a free floating exchange rate system. The CBE had devalued the currency to 13 EGP per USD, which represented a weakening of 46.3% from 8.88 EGP per USD previously. The weakening of the Egyptian pound reflects a higher cost of repayment of the external debt, therefore the value of gross debt becomes accordingly inflated by the lower value of the domestic currency. The movements in REER alongside the changes in Gross Debt to GDP ratio are depicted in Figure (9) showing an upward trend in both variables and suggesting a positive relationship between gross debt and exchange rates.

4. Methodological framework

This section provides a detailed description of the methodological framework utilized in this study. It starts by the description of data and variables selected to conduct the econometric analysis. After that the structure of the model is explained, as well as the

rationale behind imposing restrictions. Finally, the estimation procedures of the model are illustrated.

4.1. Data and selection of variables

This paper utilizes a structural vector autoregression (SVAR) approach to model the impact of various macroeconomic variables on public debt. The SVAR approach is used to examine the impact of structural shocks on the variables under study.

This model is estimated with seven variables: debt to GDP ratio, government expenditures (in logs), government revenues (in logs), RGDP (in logs), inflation rate (calculated as the % change in GDP deflator), interest rate on government debt, the change in the real effective exchange rate. The variables selected are used to examine how the debt to GDP ratio responds to structural shocks of fiscal policy tools represented in government revenues and government expenditures, macroeconomic variables represented in Real GDP and inflation rate, and finally monetary variables represented in interest rate and change in real effective exchange rate. The model uses quarterly data from 2005 to 2015. The table below shows all variables used in the analysis, with their description and reasons of selection.

VARIABLE	ABBREVIATION	VARIABLE DESCRIPTION AND RATIONALE OF CHOICE
Debt to GDP ratio	DEBTTGDP	The ratio of public debt to GDP has been used to provide a comprehensive image of the overall level of indebtedness of the country as it shows the consolidated debt of the general government and economic authorities.
Government expenditures (in logs)	LNEXPEND_D11	This variable measures all aspects of government expenditures, and hence includes purchases of goods and services, compensation of employees, interest payments and subsidies, in addition to government investments.
Government revenues in logs	LNREV_D11	Total government revenues have been utilized as this measure includes tax revenues, grants, property income, income from sale of goods and services. Hence, it provides a complete estimate of all sources of revenue to the government.
Real GDP	DLNRGDP_D11	Real, rather than nominal GDP has been utilized to represent how changes in real output levels affect public debt.
Inflation rate	INF_D11	The variable measures the percentage change in the overall price level calculated as the percentage change in GDP deflator.
Interest rate	DIR_D11	The interest rate on government debt -represented by the average rate on treasury bills and bonds- has been utilized as it is one of the primary determinants of public debt.
Change in real effective exchange rate	Changeer	The change in real effective exchange rate has been used as it represents the change in the weighted average of the local currency to a basket of major foreign currencies, after adjusting for inflation.

4.2. Structure of the model and imposing restrictions

The SVAR approach involves running two steps. First, we run traditional unrestricted VAR. Then, the analysis proceeds to estimate structural factorization by imposing restrictions based on economic theory and previous empirical literature in public debt and its response to macroeconomic variables.

A reduced form VAR, excluding the deterministic trend can be shown by equation (1).

$$Y_t = A_1 Y_{t-1} + A_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p Y_{t-p} + E_t \tag{1}$$

Where Y_t is a (nx1) vector of endogenous variables, A_i is a (n x n) vector of parameters, p denotes the number of lags in the VAR model, and finally E_t is (nx1) vector of error terms with expected value of 0. The Lag length selection in unrestricted VAR model is determined based on information criteria.

Following this step, the SVAR model is estimated through imposing restrictions. The general form of the SVAR model can be written in the form shown in equation (2).

$$A Y_t = A_1 Y_{t-1} + A_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p Y_{t-p} + B E_t \tag{2}$$

This model has been generalized by Amisano & Giannini (1997) in the form of matrices, and called AB model as shown in equation (3). The A matrix is a Lower triangular matrix that shows the coefficients of contemporaneous relationships among variables, while the B matrix shows the estimated coefficients for the lagged endogenous variables

$$A \varepsilon_t = B u_t \tag{3}$$

The identification of restrictions in SVAR model is based on putting some restrictions on contemporaneous relationships among variables. Following the approach adopted by Melecky & Melecky (2011), these restrictions are shown in equation 4, which represents the left-hand side of the standard SVAR representation. The non-zero coefficients *in matrix A* show the instantaneous effects of row variables on the column variable. The coefficients on the diagonals are normalized to one, while the 0 entries indicate that there is no contemporaneous relationship between the two variables. The main identification assumption behind the diagonal structure of the A matrix implies that government expenditures, revenues, the level of output, inflation, interest rates and exchange rates respond to changes in the debt-to GDP ratio contemporaneously but the debt to GDP ratio responds to changes in these variables only after time lag.

The system proposed in this model is exactly identified as the number of restrictions imposed on matrix A coefficients is equal to $(n^2 - n)/2$, where n is the number of variables. Thus, a total of 21 restrictions are imposed on the model. The structure of the contemporaneous relationship among the variables is presented below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ NA & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ NA & NA & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ NA & NA & NA & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ NA & NA & NA & NA & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ NA & NA & NA & NA & NA & 1 & 0 \\ NA & NA & NA & NA & NA & NA & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_t^{debt} \\ U_t^{exp} \\ U_t^{rev} \\ U_t^{RGDP} \\ U_t^{inf} \\ U_t^{ir} \\ U_t^{er} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} NA & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} E_t^{debt} \\ E_t^{exp} \\ E_t^{rev} \\ E_t^{RGDP} \\ E_t^{inf} \\ E_t^{ir} \\ E_t^{er} \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

4.3. Model estimation

The first step in the model estimation involved conducting stationarity tests to determine the stationarity of time-series data using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test. This is a crucial step in order to avoid spurious results resulting from using non-stationary time series in the model. The results of the ADF test showed that all variables are stationary except Real GDP and interest rate, which are integrated of order 1. Thus, the first difference of these two series has been used in the model.

The second step was to determine the appropriate lag length using lag length criteria. The lag length criterion (Akaike, Schwartz, & Hannan-Quinn) recommends a lag length of 2, so this lag structure is used in the model estimation.

FIGURE 10. INVERSE ROOTS OF AR-CHARACTERISTIC POLYNOMIAL

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

Before running the impulse response function, the stability of the VAR model was tested using the inverse roots graph. The model was found to be stable since all inverse roots of the estimated VAR coefficients lie inside the circle as shown in Figure (10). This implies that the impact of shocks on variables fades away after a certain period of time.

5. Results and discussion

This section presents the results of the SVAR model, showing the impact of shocks in macroeconomic variables on the debt-to-GDP ratio using Impulse Response functions (IRFs) and Variance decomposition of all variables.

Impulse response functions (IRFs)

The IRFs for 12 quarters are presented in Figure (11), which shows the impact of positive shocks in government expenditures, government revenues, real GDP, inflation, interest rates, and the exchange rate on the debt-to GDP ratio.

FIGURE 11. IMPULSE RESPONSE FUNCTIONS

Source: Drawn by the authors using Central Bank of Egypt Database.

It is evident that a positive shock in government expenditures leads to a prolonged increase in the debt-to-GDP ratio. This goes in line with theoretical expectations as an expansionary fiscal policy leads to higher debt when the mobilized revenues are not sufficient to cover all expenses. A positive shock in government revenues starts to lead to a reduction in the debt to GDP ratio after the third quarter as it takes time to adjust to this increase and reverse the upward trend in debt to GDP ratio (as shown in the descriptive analysis in section 3.2, there is a tendency to borrow more even if revenues are increasing, thus, it takes a long horizon of time to reverse the upward direction of the debt to GDP ratio when a positive shock to government revenues occur). The debt to GDP ratio

responds directly to a positive shock in the real GDP due to the need to finance this growth through domestic/external debt when revenues are not enough to finance the required investments to boost this economic growth.

In addition, a positive shock to the inflation rate leads to a reduction in the debt/GDP ratio. Although this result contradicts the direction of relationship from the descriptive analysis in section (3.2), this goes in line with empirical literature in countries with varying degrees of development (Nguyen, 2015; Akitoby et al.; 2014 and Hilscher et al., 2014) which found a significant negative impact of inflation on public debt. The rationale behind these findings is that inflation erodes the real value of public debt. Thus, highly indebted countries can escape from the debt crisis through higher inflation. Furthermore, a positive shock in inflation is probably a result for expansionary monetary policy that decreases interest rates which leads to a lower burden of domestic debt. The variation between the model findings and the descriptive analysis findings can be explained in terms of the fact that the model accounts for the conditional relationship among variables and hence controls for the effect of other variables that affect public debt, while the graphical representation showed only the unconditional relationship between inflation and public debt without controlling for the effect of other variables.

As for interest rates, a positive shock to the interest rate leads to a higher burden of debt leading to more indebtedness to repay debt, thus leading to a higher debt/GDP ratio. Finally, a positive shock to the real effective exchange rate leads to an increase in debt/GDP ratio as lower value of the domestic currency increases the cost of necessary imports, hence putting pressures on the government budget leading to higher debt to finance these costs of imports. In addition, higher exchange rate leads to a higher debt burden of external debt leading to a higher level of indebtedness to meet external debt service obligations.

Variance decomposition

The variance decomposition of the debt to GDP ratio shows the relative importance of the selected macroeconomic variables in explaining the changes in debt to GDP ratio starting from quarter 1 to 12 as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF DEBT TO GDP RATIO

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	2.133650	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	3.204697	57.37096	4.661902	1.878573	3.397642	13.93281	2.387193	16.37092
3	4.047630	40.00853	3.059846	1.238008	14.96398	20.83716	2.670822	17.22164
4	4.438557	40.17690	4.189622	1.477828	15.46448	20.33743	3.509376	14.84437
5	4.829378	38.57458	6.587725	1.283225	13.79118	19.50293	6.141170	14.11919
6	5.227403	35.22946	8.491484	1.113667	13.45317	19.39811	7.763153	14.55095
7	5.507907	33.45401	10.07878	1.060772	14.04695	19.23033	7.972934	14.15622
8	5.757455	32.29504	12.95891	1.291584	13.74468	18.56122	7.842071	13.30650
9	6.010930	30.82200	16.02462	1.399939	13.39837	17.92967	7.778684	12.64671
10	6.234753	29.42634	18.51370	1.406887	13.26299	17.51007	7.639627	12.24038
11	6.428908	28.26140	20.86455	1.462991	13.14727	17.06800	7.392893	11.80289
12	6.620740	27.14538	23.35136	1.619005	12.94123	16.50648	7.125839	11.31070

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

It shows that government expenditures is the most influential variable that explains changes in the debt-to-GDP ratio in quarter 12 as it accounts for about 23% of the changes in debt/GDP ratio. This is due to the fact that one of the main drivers of public debt is the level of government expenditures. When public expenditures exceed the mobilized public revenues, the government has to borrow whether domestically or externally to finance these expenditures, which is reflected on the debt/GDP ratio. This is followed by inflation, the real GDP and the change in exchange rate that explain 16.5%, 13% and 11.3% of the changes in the debt to GDP ratio respectively.

As for the variance decomposition of other variables in the model after 12 quarters, we note the following findings (see Tables 2-7 in Appendix 1)

Around 81% of the changes in government expenditures are due to the changes in itself, even after 12 quarters have passed. This implies that the increase in government expenditures is largely explained by the composition and structure of government expenditures. This is particularly relevant in the Egyptian economy since around 80% of government expenditures are represented in wages, subsidies and interest on debt which are financial obligations that cannot be avoided. Thus, the increase in government's expenditures annually is mainly attributed to the increase in those two crucial components. Following the changes in itself, the other influential variables explaining the changes that occur in government expenditures are represented in the real GDP and government revenues that explain 6%, and 5% respectively of the changes that occur in government expenditures. This implies that real GDP growth derive increases in government expenditures (purchases and investments) as a component of economic growth. Also, government operations tend to expand with higher growth rates. As for revenues, the changes in government expenditures are explained by changes in the revenue structure that are used to finance these government expenditures.

A significant portion (57%) of the changes in government revenues are explained by the changes in government expenditures. This is consistent with theoretical expectations as the primary driver for mobilizing more governmental revenues is financing government expenditures in various sectors. The most influential variables affecting real GDP changes are government revenues that explain around 25% of the variation in real GDP, which is consistent with previous literature that argues that higher government revenues have a significant impact on economic growth. The second influential variable is government expenditures and explains around 7% of the variations in real GDP. On the other hand, the interest rate explains only 3.5% of the changes in GDP. Thus, according to the models' findings fiscal policy has a more influential impact on real GDP than monetary policy tools during the period of study.

The most influential variables that explain changes that occur in the inflation rate are represented in the real GDP that explain 20% of the changes in inflation as the level of output determines the price level. This is followed by the debt to GDP ratio which explains 17.5% of the changes in inflation. This implies that the level of public debt is a significant variable in explaining price changes as when domestic debt increases by issuing T-bills and T-bonds, this leads to an expansion in money supply leading to higher inflation. This finding implies that inflation is not always a monetary phenomenon and that it can be caused by fiscal changes not just monetary changes (this is also consistent with the findings of Hashem (2017)). Finally, the interest rate explains around 14 % of the changes in prices.

The most significant factors that explain the changes in the exchange rate are represented in inflation, interest rate and debt to GDP ratio that explain 17.6%, 16.7% and 16% of the changes in exchange rate respectively. This can be explained by the fact that monetary variables have an influential impact on the exchange rate. Interest rates represent the return on holding the currency, thus as interest rate on domestic currency increases for example, this leads to higher incentives in selling foreign currency and converting to domestic currency to earn higher returns. Similarly, when inflation tends to increase, the purchasing power of domestic currency tends to decrease, hence the function of the currency as a store of value tends to deteriorate, which affects the exchange rate. Finally, the debt-to-GDP ratio affects the credibility of the economy and macroeconomic stability, which is a significant determinant of the value of domestic currency, hence it is one of the significant determinants of the exchange rate.

6. Research limitations

The main limitation of this research is represented in data availability. The researchers were aspiring to cover a longer time frame to provide more insights of the sensitivity of public debt to macroeconomic variables in different intervals. However, quarterly data on government revenues and expenditures were not readily available before 2005. In addition, the empirical methodology could have been strengthened by constructing a simulation model to forecast the performance of the debt-to-GDP ratio in light of changes in the model variables. However, this required building a dynamic simulation model, which can be done separately in future research work after identifying the most influential variables that affect the debt-to-GDP ratio in this work.

7. Conclusion

This paper has utilized a structural VAR approach to study the impact of macroeconomic shocks on public debt in Egypt. This is crucial in shedding light on the sensitivity of public debt to macroeconomic variables, hence providing policy makers with insights on the most influential factors to reduce the public debt burden and guarantee its sustainability. The study has revealed that government expenditures is the most influential variables that affect the debt to GDP ratio. A positive shock in government expenditures leads to a prolonged increase in the debt-to GDP ratio. This is due to the fact that an expansionary fiscal policy leads to an increase in public debt when public revenues are not sufficient to cover these expenditures. This implies that the first step in cutting public debt and designing sustainable fiscal policies is represented in decreasing government expenditures. This requires further analysis of the structure and composition of public expenditures to determine the types of expenditures that can be reduced, with the necessary time plan.

Other influential macroeconomic variables that tend to have a significant effect on public debt are represented in real GDP, inflation and exchange rate. Real GDP is an influential factor that affects the overall level of public debt due to the need to finance economic growth through domestic/external debt when revenues are not enough to finance the required investments to boost this economic growth. Inflation also affects the debt-to-GDP ratio as higher prices erode the real value of public debt. Finally, an increase in the exchange rate leads to an increase in debt/GDP ratio through increasing the cost of

necessary imports, hence putting pressures on the government budget leading to higher debt to finance these costs. In addition, higher exchange rate leads to a higher debt burden of external debt resulting in a higher level of indebtedness to meet external debt service obligations.

Further research work can focus on an in-depth analysis of the sustainability of public debt in Egypt after identifying the impact of macroeconomic shocks on public debt and determining the most influential variables that affect the debt to GDP ratio.

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Appendix

TABLE 1. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF DEBT TO GDP RATIO

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	2.133650	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	3.204697	57.37096	4.661902	1.878573	3.397642	13.93281	2.387193	16.37092
3	4.047630	40.00853	3.059846	1.238008	14.96398	20.83716	2.670822	17.22164
4	4.438557	40.17690	4.189622	1.477828	15.46448	20.33743	3.509376	14.84437
5	4.829378	38.57458	6.587725	1.283225	13.79118	19.50293	6.141170	14.11919
6	5.227403	35.22946	8.491484	1.113667	13.45317	19.39811	7.763153	14.55095
7	5.507907	33.45401	10.07878	1.060772	14.04695	19.23033	7.972934	14.15622
8	5.757455	32.29504	12.95891	1.291584	13.74468	18.56122	7.842071	13.30650
9	6.010930	30.82200	16.02462	1.399939	13.39837	17.92967	7.778684	12.64671
10	6.234753	29.42634	18.51370	1.406887	13.26299	17.51007	7.639627	12.24038
11	6.428908	28.26140	20.86455	1.462991	13.14727	17.06800	7.392893	11.80289
12	6.620740	27.14538	23.35136	1.619005	12.94123	16.50648	7.125839	11.31070

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 2. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF GOVERNMENT EXPENDITURES

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	0.144798	8.648266	91.35173	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.197296	5.229266	70.37996	6.366517	9.249012	1.285550	2.555887	4.933809
3	0.232175	4.468587	76.83203	4.889265	6.832712	0.952812	2.415754	3.608836
4	0.250122	4.493987	78.53610	4.288580	6.436752	0.969990	2.082104	3.192484
5	0.280508	4.011966	79.08880	5.301139	5.928879	1.220280	1.746121	2.702815
6	0.306143	3.548654	78.66539	5.721483	6.770860	1.437164	1.486444	2.370010
7	0.323852	3.497156	79.48413	5.477318	6.439767	1.510826	1.364242	2.226564
8	0.340172	3.358113	80.23684	5.136210	6.210489	1.617074	1.250897	2.190376
9	0.357346	3.210092	80.15134	5.288319	6.404466	1.691456	1.141049	2.113281
10	0.374072	3.126417	80.45959	5.331809	6.323413	1.683159	1.076825	1.998791
11	0.388354	3.088671	80.83036	5.172719	6.191378	1.718683	1.037201	1.960984
12	0.402111	3.038740	81.01882	5.074837	6.167438	1.783796	0.977037	1.939330

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 3. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF GOVERNMENT REVENUES

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	0.132289	5.211329	5.065079	89.72359	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.169873	9.054653	10.10703	71.46088	0.607515	0.251728	0.032646	8.485545
3	0.221444	5.333351	37.77048	45.62632	2.114082	0.973380	2.694219	5.488163
4	0.229781	5.760183	39.80240	42.45160	1.981656	1.163130	3.694231	5.146798
5	0.247119	5.122864	45.97568	37.06074	2.183681	1.248043	3.581800	4.827192
6	0.268254	4.348569	45.12353	34.41576	6.530313	1.645025	3.833888	4.102920
7	0.286956	4.086990	48.55781	32.71137	6.123831	1.450113	3.366650	3.703232
8	0.295903	3.927284	51.07001	30.79771	5.759185	1.451413	3.380011	3.614390
9	0.302682	3.781007	52.31469	29.43581	5.812648	1.632616	3.230415	3.792804
10	0.312609	3.586982	53.72634	28.34892	6.127526	1.597218	3.043180	3.569837
11	0.322359	3.515416	55.50824	27.23381	5.967127	1.520610	2.895508	3.359289
12	0.329998	3.468216	57.07583	26.02272	5.778277	1.535112	2.816808	3.303037

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 4. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF REAL GDP

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	0.025741	3.576974	0.863336	12.70059	82.85910	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.030195	3.558855	0.683177	12.16841	82.58624	0.174705	0.470563	0.358046
3	0.032180	3.134489	3.453111	18.54073	73.05993	0.273135	1.155366	0.383237
4	0.034101	2.834019	3.605030	22.66775	67.97056	0.245164	2.241012	0.436467
5	0.034460	2.798074	4.149176	22.52936	66.78309	0.350777	2.888512	0.501014
6	0.035487	2.638825	5.664832	24.17050	63.41229	0.331723	3.155002	0.626830
7	0.035751	2.607210	6.371782	24.13655	62.53112	0.332646	3.373930	0.646765
8	0.035992	2.592001	6.353146	24.61480	61.94948	0.336968	3.413937	0.739667
9	0.036053	2.596723	6.355749	24.56421	61.79933	0.388381	3.501166	0.794443
10	0.036318	2.561150	6.672207	24.93213	61.13352	0.382874	3.495792	0.822329
11	0.036439	2.568082	7.128200	24.81959	60.73211	0.387738	3.539727	0.824555
12	0.036507	2.561808	7.213095	24.87224	60.51844	0.401324	3.551592	0.881500

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 5. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF INFLATION

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	1.219968	25.12844	0.223578	0.085166	22.92737	51.63544	0.000000	0.000000
2	1.379660	22.11268	0.589359	4.341681	22.72593	45.01043	3.281858	1.938062
3	1.454719	19.90348	1.112126	3.980067	21.21116	40.58008	11.46861	1.744478
4	1.520673	18.21513	1.463156	6.655952	20.02757	37.64619	14.19828	1.793730
5	1.526153	18.11281	1.646009	6.633624	20.18730	37.44523	14.10012	1.874917
6	1.544563	17.71158	2.078043	7.374214	20.18011	36.57682	13.98829	2.090932
7	1.554605	17.50811	2.405778	7.705027	19.93163	36.14156	13.93591	2.371982
8	1.557773	17.46044	2.471221	7.813335	19.97237	35.99930	13.92006	2.363274
9	1.559984	17.50542	2.478497	7.791458	19.95597	35.90973	13.99906	2.359857
10	1.562260	17.49339	2.494233	7.876659	19.90150	35.84126	13.99103	2.401929
11	1.563523	17.47660	2.509327	7.864226	19.91737	35.84157	13.97813	2.412775
12	1.564461	17.46957	2.506883	7.908396	19.93042	35.80972	13.96211	2.412892

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 6. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF INTEREST RATES

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	0.750836	14.59807	0.389364	2.283662	9.207496	2.729591	70.79182	0.000000
2	0.974069	9.607357	3.249723	2.560799	8.885737	7.056811	68.53761	0.101966
3	1.031790	9.147002	2.913236	8.223168	8.513375	6.722149	63.08070	1.400366
4	1.067239	8.669990	3.009496	8.377800	7.959453	6.304178	63.58096	2.098127
5	1.145024	7.532073	4.144041	12.44604	7.438942	5.595326	58.15334	4.690237
6	1.153512	7.467324	4.685236	12.61194	7.492313	5.530528	57.36726	4.845401
7	1.168134	7.803378	4.708052	13.77555	7.549446	5.399011	55.94664	4.817922
8	1.175546	8.114287	5.056435	13.61745	7.455950	5.391610	55.59275	4.771522
9	1.183465	8.113864	5.018767	13.86765	7.386311	5.709931	54.91002	4.993456
10	1.186643	8.119483	4.999170	13.79811	7.543031	5.884946	54.65795	4.997307
11	1.190301	8.143690	5.054219	14.00224	7.619984	5.875053	54.33361	4.971202
12	1.192796	8.180074	5.123201	13.94459	7.588150	5.867904	54.31831	4.977774

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis.

TABLE 7. VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION OF EXCHANGE RATES

Period	S.E.	DEBTTGDP	LNEXPEND_D11	LNREV_D11	DLNRGDP_D11	INF_D11	DIR_D11	Changeer
1	2.366834	15.04998	2.266900	18.67692	4.269986	10.42475	21.77421	27.53726
2	2.856922	21.50567	10.88794	16.12521	3.417739	10.50995	18.50914	19.04435
3	3.216164	16.97548	8.910899	13.13516	8.547261	18.27848	14.74966	19.40305
4	3.303653	16.22289	10.14367	12.69738	9.147057	19.10798	14.15258	18.52844
5	3.325542	16.58707	10.05699	12.70287	9.033511	18.86177	14.47078	18.28702
6	3.398329	16.23580	9.890502	12.17649	8.650691	18.11033	16.68780	18.24839
7	3.457341	15.85578	9.555747	12.52498	8.447588	17.72484	17.38662	18.50445
8	3.469078	16.07118	9.501119	12.44895	8.509315	17.75343	17.27328	18.44274
9	3.498921	16.16407	9.872367	12.71090	8.574159	17.56626	16.98018	18.13206
10	3.523448	16.16978	10.26811	12.64521	8.611464	17.50918	16.87247	17.92379
11	3.538098	16.13604	10.34172	12.59768	8.593112	17.57312	16.83833	17.92001
12	3.546477	16.12130	10.41995	12.53825	8.647017	17.61085	16.76777	17.89486

Source: E-views output based on SVAR analysis